

RECOMBINANT AND PHOTSENSITIVITY INCREASING DEFECTS.

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Annotations. Defects in the crystal lattice are by their very nature a semiconductor creates different energy levels in the forbidden area. These energy levels ionization, i.e. near and far from conduction and valence fields to the location looking at charge of carriers to live on time each different effect shows [1-2]. The following in the picture three different activation to energy have has been half conductor given. In the picture E_1 energetic levels conductivity and valent to the fields very near is located that it was for, conductivity in the field electrons to himself pulling win received with in them electrons heat energy is transferred back to the field of conduction at the expense of kT and this process all the time may occur. Likewise near the valence band absorbing the holes in the valence field from the level where it is located and returning to its position possible [3].

Keywords. Recombinant, energetic levels, photosensitivity increasing level, interdisciplinary, recombination centers through,

In such cases, the recombination process does not occur, because the electron hole with meeting no being won't leave [4]. Such energetic levels **adhesive energetic levels** that is called

1– picture Three different activation to energy have has been semiconductor.

If the energy level is located in the middle of the forbidden region, then conductivity from the field win received electrons again conductivity back to the field exit probability will be very few because their activation since the energy is much greater than kT , *the energy level is occupied by electrons* and empty to be to the possibility looking at win received electrons valent in the field meets the cavities and mutual recombination occurs. Create an energy level depending on the electron and hole absorption surface ratio of the defect (S_n/S_p), the residence time of charge carriers is determined [5-6].

So, something energetic from the level the electron conductivity to the fieldIf the probability of release is greater than the probability of winning these levels, such energetic levels **adhesive levels**, if reverse if such levels **recombination levels** that is called [7-8].

From the conduction region of the Fermi level (by changing the temperature) orvalent from the field prohibited field to the middle shift adhesive from the level recombination centers rotation probability increases.

2 – picture Photocurrent decrease process.

Only energy levels that form defects in the middle of the forbidden region recombination levels being service does. The following in the picture adhesive energetic levels has been (1) and without them (2) only recombination levels there is when illuminating semiconductor materials with the same light pulse relaxation of the photocurrent decrease when the light pulse is turned off is shown. This relaxation from the lines charge of carriers to live the time determination possible [9-10].

Usually the lifetime of charge carriers is light after switching off equal to the time required for the stationary photocurrent to return to 50% of its value that acceptance done If half to the conductor two multiple ionization possible If the input atoms are included, for example, the donor concentration is N_d has been to silicon two energetic level harvest who does acceptor $M_s (N_a)$ the atoms and $N_a \leq 2N_d$ When the condition is met, the Zn element is the main atom of the element part Zn^{++} will be in position. In such a defect, the absorption surface of the pores S_p^{++} very much big will be But his the electron swallow surface S_p very small will be ie $S_n^- \ll S_p$. In this case, the residence time of electrons and holes increases dramatically and decreases [11-15]. Therefore, the residence time of the electron is much smaller by increasing the time, the photoconductivity can be increased accordingly will be An example for M_s atoms until entered $t_n \sim 10^{-7}$, $t_p \sim 10^{-7}$ Sec has been if, after entering ($N_{zn} \sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) $t_n \sim 10^{-4}$, $t_p \sim 10^{-10}$ sec and so corresponding $S_p^{++} \sim 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2$, $S_n^- \sim 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^2$ will be Then the photoconductivity is below expressions through when calculated

$$\Delta\sigma_o = Ik\beta(\mu_n r_{n0} + \mu_p r_{p0}) \tag{1}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_1 = Ik\beta(\mu_n r_{n1} + \mu_p r_{p1}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma_1}{\Delta\sigma_2} = 10^7 \quad (3)$$

value March increases. M_s atoms certain amount n – Input to Si with its photo sensitivity 10^7 we can increase to Therefore to Zn atoms suitable came energetic level *photosensitivity increasing level* that is called Same so p – pores by introducing S , Se , Mn atoms into different Si residence time increase possible [16-17].

Usually half conductor in materials main didn't happen charge the lifetime of the carriers is taken into account and that of the semiconductor material main from the parameters one is considered To this reason main has been charge carriers a lot that it was for their to live time they are with recombination to be done on time depend on ie main didn't happen charge to carriers depends [18-20]. Because main charge of carriers loss (out of the game) it is only non-main charge carriers, with them determined only by recombination. So, any n - in various materials the lifetime of charge carriers means the lifetime of holes in it understood. p – in the round it will be the opposite [21-24].

Recombination types

Half in conductors **recombination** electron to pass looking at two type:

- **interdisciplinary**, ie conductivity in the field of electron valent in the field with a hole direct recombination;
- **recombination centers through**, ie electron hole with recombination from being before one recombination to the center swallowing from him after that's it defect from the tool valent to the field passing by hole with recombination processes is divided.

I kind of recombination mainly _ energetic levels structure right has

been half in conductors ($GaAs$, GaP , ...) happen will be

II kind of recombination energetic levels structure wrong has been (Si, Ge ...) half conductor in the materials happen will be.

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